

Emergence of Life by Rotating Urey-Miller clouds in Abraham Loeb's theory

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Abstract:

Recently, Abraham Loeb have argued that around 7-10 million years after Big Bang, temperature of universe was 273-373 K and heavy atoms like carbon, nitrogen, hydrogen and oxygen were combined with each other and formed molecules of life like water, Amino Acids and DNA/RNAs. We propose a model which confirms the concepts of this theory and simulate Urey-Miller experiment in initial stages of universe. In this model, not only molecules of life like DNAs are emerged but also a cloud of molecules of life is created which its rotation cause to coiling and compacting of DNAs in nano-size boxes like present nucleus within cells. We show that frequencies of cosmic waves which are radiated by charged clouds, initial galaxies and other cosmic objects in this initial stage of universe are equal to frequencies of waves which are produced by motion of charges around the gates of cellular and nuclear membranes. We obtain the number of cosmic waves which are needed for explosion of cosmic life clouds and production of DNA packages.

Keywords: Biology; Cosmology; Earth; Urey-Miller; Life; Universe

Introduction

Recently, Abraham Loeb has argued that when the age of universe was 7-10 million years, heavy atoms like carbon, nitrogen and molecules of water interact with each other and form molecules of life like Amino acids and bases of DNAs and RNAs [1]. This idea is in good agreement with Urey-Miller experiment [2]. In this experiment, molecules of water became hot and their vapors were mixed with CH₄, H₂, NH₃ and some other molecules. Then, using two electrodes, some strong electromagnetic waves were radiated and let the system to become cooled. After one or some days, molecules of life like amino acids were emerged [2,3]. Up to date, many scientists have worked on this subject. For example, some authors have shown that unless habitability around low mass stars is suppressed, life is most

likely to exist near stars ten trillion years from now [4]. In another article, authors have demonstrated that high abundances of water vapor could have existed in extremely low metallicity partially shielded gas during the epoch of first metal enrichment of the interstellar medium of galaxies at high redshifts [5]. In other paper, scientists have explored the possibility of planet formation in the carbon-rich protoplanetary discs of carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars, possible relics of the early Universe [6]. In other research, to find some signatures of life, investigators have done a search for sources of directed energy systems such as those now becoming technologically feasible on Earth [7]. In another work, it has been discussed that embedding parameters such as net primary productivity, calculated using habitability indexes, into greater ecological models with several trophic models, make a clear connection between the astrobiological and ecological approaches of quantitative habitability [8]. Motivated by these researches and using Ury-Miller experiments, we will propose a new model for the habitable epoch of the early Universe.

Comparing a young universe with a cell and the Ury-Miller system

In this section, we compare three systems: 1. Cell 2. Young universe with ages around 7-10 million years old 3. Ury-Miller system. We will show that in all three systems, temperature, radiated waves and other physical properties are the same. This means that there is a mechanism for producing molecules of life in each of these systems (See figure 1). Within a cell, there are some CH_3 , molecules of water and combinations of nitrogen. These molecules are similar to molecules in Urey-Miller system. Also, gates of cells absorb or repel charges and take positive/ negative charges. Thus, these gates are similar to electrodes in Urey-Miller experiments. Sometimes activity and density of charges within cells increase and temperature can grow and then immediately reduces to normal values. This is also in agreement with Urey-Miller system so. The same conditions could be occurred within a young universe. In this system, cosmic waves play the role of electrodes in Urey-Miller system. Also, a young universe could have molecules of carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and molecules of water. These molecules interact with cosmic waves, become hot, evolve, become cooled and produce molecules of life.

To begin this discussion, we remember that in Urey-Miller experiment, first, molecules of water became hot, evaporate, combine with some carbonic, nitric and hydric molecules, interact with electrical currents between two electrodes and then became cooled. In these conditions, some molecules of life like amino acids are emerged. Temperature of cooled system is equal to temperature of medium around 273-373 K. On the other hand, temperature of a cell is also around 38-40 C or 311-

313 K. Also, according to Abraham Loeb, temperature of a universe with 7-10 million years old is around 273-373 K. This temperature is equal to temperature of cells and Urey-Miller system.

$$T_{\text{CELL}} \approx T_{\text{Universe-7-10 million year}} \approx T_{\text{Urey-Miller}} \quad (1)$$

Above equation shows that the thermal conditions of the young universe is similar to cells and Urey-Miller system. In fact, in all three systems, first, temperature grows, then, molecules interact with each other and form some complexes. After that, temperature decreases and system becomes stable.

Besides temperature, waves also play the main role in formation of molecules of life. They interact with initial molecules and divide them to separate atoms. Then, these atoms join to each other and form new amino acids, DNAs and RNAs. In Urey-Miller experiments, electrodes produce a current which emit needed waves. Within a universe, cosmic micro waves interact with atoms and help them to produce molecules of life. The frequency of these waves could be from 10^{11} - 10^{24} Hz. We can assert that the same frequencies could be observed within cells. In this system, motions of charged particles produce some electrical currents (See figure 1). These currents emit some waves which their frequencies could be equal to frequencies of some cosmic waves. Also, these charges interact with base molecules of a DNA, move them and produce second DNA currents. This is because that each DNA base is formed from charged electrons and atoms and by their motions, some waves are emerged. For example, we can write:

$$r \rightarrow 10^{-10} \leftrightarrow B = \mu_0 NI / 2\pi r \rightarrow 10^{10} (\mu_0 NI / 2\pi)$$

$$U_B = (B^2 / 2 \mu_0) \approx h \nu \leftrightarrow \nu \rightarrow 10^{20} (\mu_0 N^2 I^2 / 8h\pi^2) \approx 10^{20} (10^{26} N^2 I^2) \\ N^2 I^2 \approx \geq 10^{-26} \rightarrow \nu \approx \geq 10^{20} \quad (2)$$

Where r is the radius of DNA supercoils within the nucleus, B is the magnetic Field, U_B is the magnetic energy, h is the plank constant, I is the current and N is the number of currents. Above equation shows that depending on number and density of currents, frequencies within a cell could change around 10^{20} Hz. These frequencies are in the range of cosmic waves. These waves interact with carbonic, nitric and water molecules, divide them into separate atoms and produce Amino acids, Adenine, guanine, cytosine and thymine bases. Thus, we can simulate a young universe with a cell (See figure 1).

Fig1: Comparing a young universe with a cell and a Urey-Miller system

Emergence of a rotating cosmic cloud of molecules of life

After Big bang, first particles like electrons, quarks and some gauge fields like photons may be produced. Eventually, hadrons and barons are emerged. After a period of time, some light atoms like hydrogen and helium are created. By passing time, light atoms interact with each other and some heavy atoms like carbons, nitrogen and oxygen are produced. These atoms join to each other and form, molecules of life like molecules of water, amino acids, and DNA bases. DNA bases and other life's molecules may join to each other and form a cosmic cloud. This cosmic cloud could interact with other charged cosmic clouds and rotate. The velocity of this rotation could be so much that some parts of cloud become coiled around different axes and then separated from initial cloud. Shape of these separated child clouds could be very similar to the shape of DNAs. These separated clouds interact with cosmic waves, divide into smaller parts which each new part become compacted within some boxes. These boxes could be the initial and parents of present cells (See figure 2).

Now, the questions arise that how much waves and frequencies are needed that a cloud of hexagonal/pentagonal molecules of life explodes and present DNAs and cells are emerged? To response this question, we consider the process of extraction of DNAs within cells. In this process, a vessel of cells should be located within a centrifuge and rotates between 1000-10000 times in a minute (Ω_{DNA}). Assume that radius of rotation be smaller than $10^{-10}(r_{rotate})$. Thus, velocity of DNAs within cells is:

$$V_{DNA} \approx 2\pi r_{rotate} (10^9 \text{ DNA size}) \Omega_{DNA} \approx (10)(10^{-1})(10^9)(1000) \approx 10^{12} \text{ DNA/second} \quad (3)$$

Above velocity shows that in each second, a DNA should rotates 10^{12} times. If we assume that the same vibration and velocity could also cause to its compaction, we can generalize calculations to a cosmic cloud. This means that if a cloud rotates 10^{12} times in each second, it could have coiling and compacting similar to a DNA. Suppose that radius of a cloud be more than 50000 years of light or

$$\text{Radius of cloud} \geq 50000 \text{ years of light} \geq (50000) (3)(10^8) (31536000) \geq 10^{21} \text{m} \quad (4)$$

Thus, the velocity of this cloud becomes:

$$V_{\text{Cloud}} \approx \geq 10^{12} \text{ Cloud/second} \geq 10^{33} \text{ m/s} \geq (10^{33})(10^{12}) \geq 10^{45} \text{ DNA/second} \quad (5)$$

Above equation shows that if a cloud moves with 10^{33} m/s or 10^{45} DNA/second, it could be curved and divide into separate compacted DNAs. Using this velocity and total charge of a DNA, we can obtain the current of cloud:

$$Q_{\text{DNA}} \approx N_{\text{gene}} q_{\text{gene}} \approx N_{\text{gene}} N_{\text{base}} q_{\text{base}} \approx 5 \times 10^{-5} \quad (6)$$

$$\rightarrow I_{\text{Cloud}} \approx \geq Q_{\text{DNA}} V_{\text{Cloud}} \approx \geq (10^{45})(5 \times 10^{-5}) \approx \geq 10^{40} \quad (7)$$

Above current, helps us to calculate the magnetic energy and number of emitted waves:

$$\begin{aligned} U_B &= (B^2/2 \mu_0) \approx N_{\text{wave}} h \nu \leftrightarrow N_{\text{wave}} \nu \rightarrow 10^{-21} (\mu_0 I^2/8h\pi^2) \approx 10^{-21} (10^{26} I^2) \\ (I_{\text{Cloud}})^2 &\approx \geq 10^{80} \rightarrow N_{\text{wave}} \nu \approx \geq 10^{-21} (10^{26} I^2) \approx \geq (10^{-21})(10^{26})(10^{80}) \approx \geq 10^{85} \\ \nu &\approx \geq 10^{20} \rightarrow N_{\text{wave}} \approx \geq 10^{65} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Above equation shows that if 10^{65} waves with frequencies between 10^{20} - 10^{24} Hz achieve to a cloud of molecules of life, this system could divide into compacted and coiled DNAs and produce cells similar to present ones. These frequencies and number of waves were very natural for a young universe. Thus, a mixture of Abraham Loeb theory with Urey-Miller experiment could describe the mechanism of the emergence of life million years before formation of present planets.

Fig 2: Emergence of life by rotating cosmic clouds within the young universe

Conclusion:

In this paper, we have reconsidered the Abraham Loeb idea about emergence of life around 7-10 million years after Big Bang. We have assumed that some

cosmological objects or planets within initial universe are similar to a container in Urey-Miller experiment and include heavy atoms like carbon, oxygen, nitrogen and hydrogen. These atoms combine to each other and form molecules of like water, amino acids and bases. These molecules of life join to each other and form a cloud. By rotating this cloud, these molecules are coiled and compacted within the nuclear and cellular membranes. These structures will be closed to present structures of cells and build blocks of life. We have calculated frequencies of emerged waves within cells and found that they are equal to frequencies of cosmic waves which are radiated by rotating charged clouds and cosmic objects of the young universe.

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